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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****NOVEL GENE IDENTIFICATION USING THE TRANSPOSE
ELEMENTS IN *RHODOCOCCUS
AETHERIVORANS* PLASMID PRA3 FOR FUTURE NOVEL
DRUG GENE TESTING****Anas Alfadda, Mishal Al Ammar and Abdulaziz Abed, Abdulrahman Alfadhel**
Alfaisal University, P.O.Box 50927, Riyadh 11533, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Genome annotation has a huge impact in molecular biology, therefore making an annotated data base using Artemis the genome browser program will allow certain researchers to have a database that they can depend on in new research. Using a program called Artemis, we created a database from a plasmid in bacteria called Rhodococcus aetherivorans which contains 350,000 base pairs and contains 207 genes.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Genome Annotation is a process of identifying genes in a genome. This is advancing rapidly, making a new era in molecular biology. It has led to some immense breakthroughs in the last few years, for example, getting a better understanding of the human genome and many bacterial genomes. Genome Annotation deals with millions of letters (the DNA bases A,T, G and C) that are difficult to understand, but by revealing the potential in them it could lead to huge developments in biological and medical sciences. Also, of particular interest to this project, annotating DNA will give us greater scope to understand the diversity and structure of microbial ecosystems.

There are three centers that focus their work on developing new programs for annotating the genome: J. Craig Venter Institute, The Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute (WTSI) and The Arabidopsis Information Resource (TAIR). Each of these

companies has developed a program that annotates DNA, and compiled databases of the annotated genome open for public use. Many researchers' entire work depends on a certain database that has been uploaded previously by another person. In the future, developing a new database will provide greater opportunities for discovery. Scientists in WTSI created a program called Artemis, developed at the Sanger Institute, which is used to annotate the genome.

Artemis is a program that was created in 1999. It is the main tool in annotating and viewing sequenced data in microbial genomes. It became famous in 2002. It has become the main tool in annotating pathogenic microbial genomes. The tools that it uses to annotate the DNA in the genome include Open reading frames, Blast search, Edit window, navigator tool and many others. Artemis is a tool that is not only used to annotate the genome but also to visualize and analyze.

Figure 1: Displays how Artemis works

Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) is a double stranded helix encoding genetic information that controls cellular functions. It is a polymer of the monomer nucleotides adenine (A), guanine (G), cytosine (C) and thymine (T). The sequence of these nitrogen base pairs encodes genes in a triplet code. Each triplet encodes one of twenty amino acids that make up all proteins, which are linear polymers of amino acids. Each gene encodes one protein. Each gene has a start signal (ATG or GTG) followed by a series of codons encoding the protein and terminated by a stop codon (TAG or TGA or TAA). Codons made of three nitrogen bases.

DNA encodes genes as triplets of bases that encode the linear organization of amino acids building blocks within a protein. These triplets are known as codons (see figure 2 below). Using triplets of any four bases allows for $4^3 = 64$ different three letter words. There are only 20 amino acids and so there is a level of redundancy – more than one codon encodes the same amino acid, e.g. ACT, ACC, ACA and ACG all encode Threonine. However, ATG (Methionine) encodes a translation start signal as well as the amino acid itself and TAG, TAA and TAA encode translation termination signals.

		Second base in codon				
		U	C	A	G	
First base in codon	U	Phe	Ser	Tyr	Cys	U
		Phe	Ser	Tyr	Cys	C
		Leu	Ser	STOP	STOP	A
		Leu	Ser	STOP	Trp	G
C	Leu	Pro	His	Arg	U	
	Leu	Pro	His	Arg	C	
	Leu	Pro	Gln	Arg	A	
	Leu	Pro	Gln	Arg	G	
A	Ile	Thr	Asn	Ser	U	
	Ile	Thr	Asn	Ser	C	
	Ile	Thr	Lys	Arg	A	
	Met	Thr	Lys	Arg	G	
G	Val	Ala	Asp	Gly	U	
	Val	Ala	Asp	Gly	C	
	Val	Ala	Glu	Gly	A	
	Val	Ala	Glu	Gly	G	

Figure 2: The 20 amino acids

The DNA translation machinery (the ribosome) reads messenger RNA in triplets on either strand. Thus there are six different frames (Figure 3).

184	204	224	244	264
Y S N * * C S S Y L L G D P V Q F P L D T I W N F N I S * * T A H H				
I P I D N V P H T C W E I L F N F H W T P S G T S T F H N K Q H I				
F Q L I M F L I L A G R S C S I S I G H H L E L Q H F I I N S T S				
T A T T C C A A T T G A T A A T G T T C C T C A T A C T T G C T G G G A G A T C C T G T T C A A T T T C C A T T G G A C A C C A C T T G G A C T T C A C A P T T C A T A A T A A A C A G C A C A T C				
A T A A G G T T A A C T A T T A C A A G G A G T A T G A A C G A C C C C T A G G A C A A G T T A A A G G T A A C C T G T G T A G A C C T T G A A G T T G T A A A G T A T T A T T T G C T G T G T A G				
I G I S L T G * V Q Q S I R N L K W Q V G D P F V E V N * L L C C M				
E L Q Y H E E Y K S P S G T * N G N S V M Q F K L M E Y Y V A C				
N W N I I N R M S A P L D Q E I E M P C W R S S * C K M I F L V D				

Figure 3: shows the six translations

In the absence of any other data, we do not know which of the frames are the real encoding frames. That is why we look for evidence to support a particular reading frame region is a gene. The evidence can include:

1. Presence of a start ATG codon
2. Presence of a stop TAG, TAA, TGA codon
3. Length of open reading frame (typically > 100 amino acids, bacterial genes are on average 300-500 amino acids long).
4. Conservation of predicted amino acid sequence with other microorganisms.

This project deals with *Rhodococcus* bacteria, specifically *Rhodococcus aetherivorans* because it has not been annotated before. Bacterial genomes are by comparison with human genomes very small and very data dense. There is almost no non-coding DNA in a bacterial genome. The bacterial genome consists of a single chromosome typically ranging in size from 500 Kb to 10 Mb. This encodes all essential functions of the cell and is capable of replicating autonomously using replication proteins encoded on the chromosome. In addition, there are

ancillary DNA elements called plasmids, which are dispensable for cell functions (Figure 4). Plasmids replicate autonomously but require chromosomally encoded replication proteins to replicate. A plasmid is a DNA molecule in the bacterium that has a

circular or linear structure. In this project, the *Rhodococcus* plasmid pRA3 will be used for annotation using Artemis. pRA3 stands for Plasmid *Rhodococcus aetherivorans* 3 Bacterium. *Rhodococcus* is not a pathogenic bacterium.

Figure 4: Displays chromosome and plasmids in a typical bacterium

Plasmids are a specialized DNA molecule that provides a genetic resource to the haploid bacterial genome. Plasmids are capable of both vertical transmission by replication and horizontal transmission by conjugation, transformation or transfection (See figure 5). In other word, plasmids provide a route for new genes to be included into the bacterial genome. This is typically how drug resistance is transmitted in pathogenic bacteria.

Figure 5: Shows the three ways of horizontal transmission

Plasmids are the major component of a group of related mobile genetic elements that also includes phages and transposons. Phages are plasmid-like structures that encode a protein coat allowing them to leave the cell as DNA/protein complexes and infect other microbes. Transposons are small DNA sequences that encode an enzyme transposase that recognizes and cuts at recognition sequences at each end of the transposon allowing the transposon to duplicate itself (Figure 6). Transpose genes are elements found in every DNA sequence. A transposon element can change its position by moving around using a DNA intermediate or an RNA intermediate. It can also

move around in horizontal flow.

Figure 6: showing the basic structure of a transposon and mechanism of transposition.

This project will examine the transposons present in pRA3. Transposons frequently integrate in plasmid DNA and can pick up novel genes and transfer them to other plasmids. To investigate the location of transposons within the large pRA3 genome, the first step in examining the possible role of transposons in the evolution of pRA3.

This project sought to identify and locate all transposon elements present in the pRA3 genome. This includes annotating the pRA3 genome and locating transpose genes within it. This will eventually be incorporated into a database to help biologists in their research in this field.

2.0 METHODOLOGY:

2.1 Inserting pRA3 sequence

Rhodococcus aetherivorans encode three different plasmids with different numbers of kilo basepairs (Kb): pRA1 (10 Kb circular), pRA2 (89 Kb circular) and pRA3 (350 Kb linear). pRA3 was used because it is the largest and most complex plasmid (350,000 bp). We were given the pRA3 DNA sequence. This was loaded into Artemis to allow us to list the base pairs and hence to start the annotating process.

2.2 Mark open reading frames

The frames start with a stop codon and end with a stop codon. Marking the reading frames produces blue lines on the screen (See Figure 7).

Figure 7: Displays blue lines that were produced by marking the open reading frames

Each blue line marks an open reading frame (ORF) and therefore represents a potential gene. Blue lines will appear after using the Mark open reading frame tool.

We look for the following evidence to predict that a particular reading frame region is a gene:

1. Presence of a start ATG codon
2. Presence of a stop TAG, TAA, TGA codon
3. Length of open reading frame (typically > 100 amino acids, bacterial genes are on average 300-500 amino acids long).
4. Conservation of predicted amino acid sequence with other microorganisms.

2.3 BLAST search

The BLAST (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool) search tool is the main tool used in identifying conservation of amino acid sequence between an ORF and known genes in other bacteria in worldwide databases. The program has a lot of applications such as identifying genes. By selecting one of the open reading frames then running the BLAST search it will show the possibilities for each protein and its chance to appear in this gene. A scale called an E value, a number used to show the likelihood of getting a similar match between the

query sequence and the database, determines the values. The greater the E number value, the less likely the match observed would occur by chance and the greater the likelihood that the match represents a statistically valid identification. For example: if a gene has an E value of -10 for a family protein and -25 E value for a replication protein, then we can assume with some confidence that the open reading frame encodes a replication protein.

After viewing the identified protein and comparing the E we obtain the probabilities of which protein will appear in the selected gene.

2.4 Determination of Transposon genes using GC graph

An Additional way can be used to further determine the Transposon genes in this plasmid is by using the GC graph. The GC graph is a graph that shows the levels of two nitrogen bases which are Guanine and Cytosine. In this Plasmid the average level of the GC content is 65.06. This means that if a foreign gene enters the plasmid the balance will be disturbed, Thus it can be determined whether a transposon genes entered the plasmid or not. (See Figure 8 and 9).

Figure 8: GC Graph with significant rise

Figure 9: GC Graph with significant drop

2.5 Editing the Genes

The open reading frames marked by Artemis start adjacent to the preceding in frame stop codon and terminate at the next in frame stop codon. They do not mark initiator codons. Following BLAST analysis to identify open reading frames with protein coding potential, the ORFs are edited to start at the appropriate start codon. First, the normal genes are colored purple to show that they are sequenced. After that, they are named. For example: A gene

results in a family protein. We color the gene purple and name the protein a family protein. The gene will make the database more organized and clearer for the public.

Finding the transposon gene is the goal in this project. They will be colored in a different color, bright green (Figure 10), in order to differentiate between them and the normal genes colored in purple.

Figure 10: showing the transposase genes colored in bright green

2.6 Navigating the start of the protein

Artemis Program contains a tool which navigates the start of the gene. Marking the open reading frames will only show the genes from a stop codon to a stop without showing the start. Therefore, using this tool will help in locating the starts of the gene to know where the gene really starts. Doing this will help us to be more specific and provide more clarity for the users of this database. The tool that is used in this step is called Artemis Navigator tool. This tool will locate the data that is inserted in the gene.

The last tool we use is trimming tool. It will move the starting position of the gene to a certain point. There are two ways of moving the gene: either to any or to initiation codon ATG Methionine.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In this project, 207 predicted genes were mapped in the pRA3 genome. From this, 11 transposase genes were identified and mapped. Also, 11 novel genes were discovered. A summary of the results of this project for the annotation of the whole pRA3 and the locating of its transposase genes is shown in Figure 11.

CDS	32521	33513	hypothetical protein USDA257_p05280 [Sinor
CDS	33026	33304	hypothetical protein NCER_102403 [Nosema c
CDS	33212	33526	c putative short-chain dehydrogenase/reducta
CDS	33401	33619	conserved unknown protein [Ectocarpus sili
CDS	33533	34009	c GntR family transcriptional regulator [Pse
CDS	33656	34066	hypothetical protein GOSPT_026_00130 [Gord
CDS	34070	34564	transposase, partial [Rhodococcus imtechen
CDS	34367	34723	c NUDIX hydrolase [Halomicrobium mukohataei
CDS	34405	35802	c hypothetical protein GOSPT_026_00150 [Gord
CDS	34724	35356	c hypothetical protein EGM_04678 [Macaca fas
CDS	34762	35310	PPE family protein [Mycobacterium tubercul
CDS	34818	35432	c hypothetical protein RO3G_17083 [Rhizopus
CDS	35280	35879	alpha-L-fucosidase [Streptococcus oralis S
CDS	35311	36219	transposase IS111A/IS1328/IS1533 [Frankia
CDS	35489	35665	hypothetical protein W59_10619 [Rhodococcu
CDS	36228	36437	hypothetical protein UUA_11848 [Rhodanobac
CDS	36249	36596	c mismatch repair-related protein [Cryptococ
CDS	36346	37449	c hypothetical protein MAP2156 [Mycobacteriu
CDS	36376	37551	hypothetical protein X001310 [Xanthomonas
CDS	36593	37498	c alpha/beta hydrolase fold protein [Polarom
CDS	37305	37667	c transposase IS3/IS911 family protein [Myco
CDS	37645	38523	Total score Query coverage E value Max id
CDS	37686	38105	hypothetical protein RHA1_ro08780 [Rhodoco
CDS	37745	38524	c hypothetical protein Pmar_PMAR015729 [Perk
CDS	37997	38389	flavin reductase domain-containing FMN-bin
CDS	38490	38819	c apolipoprotein N-acyltransferase [Treponem
CDS	38619	39872	integrase catalytic subunit [Mycobacterium

Figure 11: Displays the annotated genes in purple and the transposase in green

This analysis revealed that the pRA3 genome encodes a significant number of different transposon elements. Transposition into pRA3 appears to have occurred across the entire genome with particular 141 hot spots. This observation would suggest that transposition has occurred multiple times in the evolution of pRA3 involving different transposon elements.

4. FUTURE WORK:

This initial mapping of the transposon elements in pRA3 can be developed to investigate the transposon elements involved. This would require a sequence conservation based analysis of the different transposase genes to group them into families/types. In addition, the flanking sequences of each transposase gene can be investigated to identify the inverted repeat sequences that flank and define the element more fully. Also, to further annotate and identify the 11 novel genes those were discovered.

5. CONCLUSION:

The goal of the project is to annotate the plasmid of bacteria *Rhodococcus aetherivorans* which contained 350,000 base pairs and the location of the transposase genes that encodes valuable protein.

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